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The Role of Democratization in the School Management: Experience of High School No.6 in Baku

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Abstract

There are a number of principles that are used to effectively organize intra-school management. In the school management process, these principles must be followed consistently and positively. In this article, democratization is viewed as a principle and not a tool and process, but a principle that applies to all functions and functions of management. In the example of high school No.6 in Baku city reveals the impact of the transition from "director-employee" stage to co-worker. It is justified that in the process of co-operation the democratic leadership style is established, scientific and cognitive and methodological development of the teacher is provided, and the level of professionalism is increased. The style of democratic leadership is based on the principles of mutual respect, humanism, equality and justice. The way to democratize the school is to modernize the organizational structure of intra-school management

Keywords: school, management, director, competence, democratization.

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Introduction

Ineffective organization of intra-school management refers to a number of principles (purposefulness, principality, objectivity, scientific character, business, planning and control, etc.); among them, the principle of democracy has its importance. Research shows that improving the quality of modern school management, creating an educational, nurturing and developmental environment at school, and achieving democratic changes depend on the importance of the democratization of those who run the education system. Democratization in educational institutions envisages "the education of students in the spirit of free-thinking, the expansion of powers and freedoms in the organization and management of public education, and increasing the autonomy of educational institutions" (Ministry of Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan, 2010). This is due to the objective demands of the modern society of a new, free, responsible, creative, innovative and critical thinker, capable of making the right decisions in any life situation, capable of solving complex and contradictory problems. The modern man is selected for his co-operation in the effective use of sophisticated technology and innovation, respecting different ideas, national and human values, and having a democratic outlook. The formation of these high moral values in the younger generation depends on the democratization of public school management.

Democratization of intra-school management is the gradual expansion of school community members (students, educators), parents, and community representatives in school management, analyzing their performance, making decisions, monitoring, evaluating and evaluating their results is understood. This issue has particular relevance to the Azerbaijani education system. There is always an authoritarian approach to intra-school management in traditional (mollahana and madrasa), secular (accident schools, elementary schools, Russian-Muslim schools, gymnasiums and progymnasiums) and Soviet (I grade, II grade schools, secondary schools, etc.) schools, and the head of the school was considered a leader. Although school management, school board and all organizations were involved in the management of secondary schools in the 1970s and 1980s, these positive trends did not lead to significant changes in the absence of democracy in the country. There was a centralized system within intra-school management, the rules of transferring orders and decrees "from high position" to low position". This kind of management pleased the school principals because they were simple, easy and convenient. This form of school management stemmed from the democratization and authoritarianism of the administration, and it was in full agreement with the character of the educators and the general public at that time. Educators and students regarded it as the only possible option.

Changes in the status of educational institutions in the new socio-economic environment resulted in the change and modernization of the traditional management system. The essence of an effective management

system has changed dramatically. Assessment of managerial activities by plan and form of employment was replaced by an assessment of the final result. Effective management of the implementation of goals and tasks with fewer resources, time and effort was considered. This necessitated a new approach in defining the tasks, principles and functions of management activities.

The main object of educational institutions is the pedagogical process. The pedagogical process itself is a comprehensive and complex process. Providing the unity of training, education, upbringing and development based on completeness and generality is the core of the pedagogical process. Since the pedagogical process involves sub-systems, its effectiveness also depends on the effectiveness (effectiveness) of the subsystems. As the results of the pedagogical process depend on the proper organization of the teaching, education, upbringing process, teacher-student collaboration, the conditions in which the pedagogical process takes place, the technologies and innovations used, as well as depends on the proper arrangement the cooperation of the school principal (principals) and teachers. Teachers' professional development, objective and transparent assessment of their activities, motivation of teachers for productive and creative activities, the creation of favourable psychological environment in the teaching staff, timely support and support for teachers in complex teaching situations are at the top of the agenda in intra-school management. The principle of democratization is manifested in all areas of school life - in communication and relationships, in leadership, in the organization of pedagogical process and in intra-school management. As the scope of this principle is broad, the form of manifestation is different. In the teaching-methodical literature they are systematized as follows: state and public administration of education, respect for the rights and freedoms of teachers and students, enhancing the authority of self-governing bodies, enhancing the autonomy of educational institutions, the use of democratic leadership, involvement of parents and students in active participation in school life. When intra-school management is democratized, responsibility, rights and authority for the outcome of the educational process are shared among all participants in the process, i.e. decentralization occurs. Hence, this principle also contributes to the formation of a humanistic approach to school life.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the study is to give a comprehensive theoretical review of the role of democratization in the school management on the example of high school No.6 in Baku.

Literature review

The transition of intra-school management to democratic basics is possible only when teachers and students (self-management of a student is considered) are actively involved in this process when the

optimum ratio of horizontal and vertical relationships is established. The structure of the school consists of elements of relative independence (directors, deputy directors, psychologists, teachers, students, parents, etc.). It is essential to create the necessary conditions for the personal, social, and collective interests of those involved in intra-school management. Distribution of managerial responsibilities, while giving independence to those involved in management, has weakened the principle of internal centrality, but is characterized by the strengthening of their independence and creative initiatives. Without referring to this legitimacy, it is impossible to democratize management. Practice shows that the activities of teachers and students involved in solving certain problems are not the same. It is natural. The event organizers (school community-organizations, classroom leaders, etc.) make the mistake of expecting the same result from all students. In this case, the requirements of the principle of cooperation and humanism are violated. Although all students are involved in the solution of problems, it is important to ensure that they work until they reach their full potential. The key issue here is not just how many people work less, but also those who work with their initiation actively.

As it is important to know the regularities of management, the levels and functions of management in the democratization and humanization of intra-school management, it is equally important to clarify the conditions for the active participation of school board members in the implementation of these functions. "Management" is one of the common concepts. Management is necessary not only in technical and production areas but also in social and pedagogical systems. Management in scientific and pedagogical literature refers to activities aimed at making reasonable decisions, organizing, controlling, regulating, analyzing and completing the work (Podlasiy, 2005, p.167). The purpose of management activities is the beginning, which defines the general functions, methods and forms of management, content, and general direction. M. Potashnik's views on school management have interesting sides. In his view, school management is a purposeful activity of all subjects, ensuring dynamic development, optimal functioning and stability of the school (Potashnik, 1990, p.38). Two aspects are important in this approach: the first is that any management is purposeful, and secondly it is different from other activities. There is a need for management when people want to combine what they cannot do separately. At this point, common goals are formed, and joint activities are created to achieve these goals. The challenges faced are being addressed in the management process. Collaboration during management is purposeful, not spontaneous and chaotic. Secondary schools are the objects of intra-school management. Management activity finds its concrete expression in the actions and operations that a person performs in the management process. This activity has a relatively closed cycle. Thus, "the cycle of management begins with the goal setting and ends with the achievement of the goals. Once the intended goal is achieved, a new goal is set and the management cycle begins again (Orlov, 1974, p.71). During each cycle, the management process performs a series of actions and operations that interoperate each other. The achievement of optimal results in intra-school

management depends on the planned and purposeful interaction of the participants of the educational process.

That is why it is recommended that pedagogical literature take into account the following intra-school regularities:

- Dependence of the effectiveness of the management system on the level of structural and functional relations between the subject and the object of management;
- Dependence of the content and methods of educational work, the content and methods of the organization of the pedagogical process at school;
- The analytical, rational, humanistic, and democratic nature of management depends on the readiness of school leaders to administer various types of management activities (Pashayev & Rustamov, 2012).

For example, when a deputy director assigns one of his subordinates (for example, a class leader), he acts as a subject in relation to his subordination. The deputy director reports to the head of the school about the results of his or her activities and acts as an object. A set of methods and tools for managing, regulating, and managing the pedagogical process are called management functions. The management function is related to the scope and types of management activities. Management is driven by management responsibilities. Founder of classical management theory A. Fayol lists five types of management functions: planning, organization, giving dispose, coordination, control (Wren & Bedeian, 2002). This classification of A. Fayol long time passed. For this reason, new classifications of management functions have emerged. There is no specific number of types of management functions in pedagogical literature. In addition to planning, organizing, directing and supervising, Mr. Kuns and S. Donnel add work with employees to their classifications.

Methodology

The research was conducted on the example of the high school No.6 in Baku. Ismikhhanov and Bakhtiyarova (2012) divide the functions of the school principal into 4 parts: 1) planning and forecasting; 2) organizational disposing; 3) control-methodical; 4) Management of financial and economic activities of the school. In other studies, the functions of the school principal are defined as follows:

- 1) plans and organizes the educational process, monitors its progress and results, is responsible for the quality and effectiveness of educational work:

- 2) represents the interests of educational institution in state and public bodies;
- 3) creates the necessary conditions for the organization of extra school and extra class activities;
- 4) elects his deputies, determines their functional duties, places teaching staff in the educational institution;
- 5) employs and dismisses pedagogical, administrative, teaching staff of the educational institution;
- 6) applies the advanced forms and methods of education for the creative development of pedagogical staff of the educational institution, provide them with opportunities for conducting pedagogical experiments;
- 7) uses of budget funds allocated to educational institutions in accordance with established procedure;
- 8) bears responsibility for its activities before the relevant education authorities (Pashayev & Rustamov, 2012).

In the exemplary statute of secondary school is provided a broad and comprehensive description of the school principal's responsibilities. There it is shown that the head of the school and the management of the pedagogical process at the secondary school is the director. School director:

- 1) plans the organization of the educational process, oversees its implementation, is responsible for the quality and effectiveness of the school, represents its interests in the state and public bodies;
- 2) hires and dismisses deputies, teaching, administrative and support staff and personnel, defines functional duties among deputies;
- 3) creates the necessary conditions for the organization of extra school and extra class activities;
- 4) organizes effective use of budget and school funds allocated for educational institution;
- 5) encourages financially and spiritually motivated teachers to achieve greater results and creativity;
- 6) creates the conditions for the development of creativity and searching of pedagogical staff of the school, the use of advanced forms and methods of teaching, carrying out educational experiments;

- 7) acquires the necessary inventory, equipment as required by the normative documents, organizes current and capital repair of buildings and installations;
- 8) taking into account the suggestions and recommendations of the school board and the pedagogical council, determines the necessary measures to implement the goals and objectives of the school and organizes their implementation;
- 9) appeals to the relevant authorities in case of violation of the provisions of the current legislation on any matter related to the activities of the school and its collective members;
- 10) listens to the reports of individual teachers, class leaders, educators, deputy directors, offers suggestions for improving their work;
- 11) identifies and implements school components together with the teaching staff;
- 12) submits proposals to the special commission under the governing bodies for the assignment of specialties to teachers; recommends pedagogical staff to take professional development courses and internships (including course in abroad); provides pedagogical and other staff of the school with various types of incentives, as well as financial incentives from school funds;
- 13) represents the school in its relations with physical and legal entities, enters into contracts on its behalf, issues orders and dispose necessary to ensure the normal functioning of the school and performs other actions not prohibited by the legislation of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

The Ministry of Education, the state governing body, is closely involved in the management of secondary schools within its rights and powers, conducts diagnostic assessments to improve the professionalism of educators, selects and deploys new teachers and principals. As the democratization of good and quality school management in Azerbaijan is seen as a necessity, the use of management methods requires a new methodological approach. Management methods are multidimensional and multidimensional.

Methods in school management are applied depending on the nature and content of managed objects and processes, events. Management ends with a goal setting and achieving the expected outcome. The outcome has a positive impact on the efficiency and harmony of the pedagogical process.

Results

For this reason, special emphasis is placed on the implementation of the general functions of management theory as a whole, reflecting the management process. Management functions are the type of management activities carried out through certain operations. General management functions reflect the management process as a whole. This includes analysis and forecasting, goal setting and planning, organization, control and regulation, accounting. In some studies, although the essence is the same, the functions are expressed differently (pedagogical monitoring, planning, organizational activity, control and regulation). With the application of these common functions, the management cycle is complete. Expected results should be identified to begin the new management cycle. The advantage of this modern approach is that it is possible to perform accurate diagnostics, forecasting and projection. At the end of the school year, our school conducts annual pedagogical monitoring at the school No. 6 in Sabail district of Baku city, analyzes the successes and achievements in all areas of school life; is determined. Only after that, based on the analysis of the results of the school year, the main goals and objectives for the new school year are set, and the expected results are formed. Implementation of proper educational monitoring plays an important role in improving the quality of school management. Because here some operations are carried out:

- 1) collection and classification of information about school situation;
- 2) preliminary processing and analysis of information;
- 3) diagnosis of the condition;
- 4) forecasting; determination of purpose and specific duties.

Unlike traditional forms of control, the use of modern technology is more preferred for effective pedagogical monitoring (analysis and forecasting). During pedagogical monitoring large volumes of information are processed, analyzed, results are realized in the course of action, and time is saved. Pedagogical monitoring takes a special place in the structure of the management cycle. Any management cycle consisting of consecutive, interconnected and related functions begins and ends with it. Exclusion of pedagogical monitoring from the general management system leads to its collapse. At the same time, the functions of planning, organization, control, and regulation do not gain logical justification or conclusion in their development. The effectiveness of pedagogical and managerial activities is determined by how much a school principal and teacher knows about the methodology of pedagogical monitoring. School leaders should keep in mind that the duty of monitoring is to create a general picture of the process, from the various types of data that are more disruptive, to reflecting specific events and facts, and to identify

specific patterns and trends. The main purpose of pedagogical monitoring is to study trends in the pedagogical process, objective assessment of its results and preparation of recommendations. While optimizing management, the most appropriate option should be chosen, the conditions must be considered, the preference for collegial management, and the requirements of regulatory and legal documents related to management should be obeyed. The management of any pedagogical system involves setting goals and making decisions. The purpose of educational work and improvement of decision-making is due to the importance of developing the pedagogical system towards democratization. Proper organization of pedagogical monitoring laid the foundation for the second function of management-planning. This is a very important function of management.

The goal is the basis of all activities. An annual action plan for the school is being developed, and the pedagogical council seriously discuss and approve. Accurate goal setting in management leads to increased efficiency and enables better organization of activities. Indefinite purpose prevents obtaining the desired result. Targeting of purpose is accomplished through a set of operations: (a) definition of primary purpose; b) a summary of it; c) Accurate purpose setting. The most important way to democratize intra-school management is to jointly develop goals, identify the areas of responsibility of each participant, and align the goals of the pedagogical team with the overall objectives of the school. It allows minimizing intra-school conflicts, enhancing co-operation, and avoiding tighter control, which facilitates the separation of powers and facilitates decentralization of management. Consequently, the "interests - goals" in the management cycle are centred in the chain of "requirements – interests – goals – decisions – actions – outcomes" (Lazarev, 2005, p. 52). When the interests of the participants of the intra-school management are aligned with the goals of management, the interests act as a stimulus for the management of the school team's members. In this case, humanism and democracy of management becomes a necessity that is understood by all participants in the educational process. According to democratic management, public, collective and personal interests must be aligned to achieve a common goal, ensuring their harmony and ultimately achieving a balance of interests (Conarjevskiy, 2000). The activity of the management subject in the administrative environment of the management system is aimed at the unconditional fulfilment of the requirements of the school work. According to the management theory, effective intra-school management is the expression of the interests and goals of the community, school principal, teachers, students and parents. It is important to create realistic opportunities for the management of the participants to combine their interests around the common goal. Each interested side should have the opportunity to participate in the implementation of the set objectives, to participate in the management cycle by participating in the analysis and evaluation of the school's achievements. Experience shows that setting the goal properly facilitates planning. Planning is a type of mental activity aimed at establishing future directions of action and defining its stages of implementation. A well-thought-out plan plays an important role in the

implementation of management objectives. Planning is carried out through a number of operations: 1) modelling of future activities to achieve the goal; 2) defining the main directions of management activity; 3) defining the stages of achievement of the set goal; 4) determination of the period of execution at each stage and the responsible person; 5) agreement and approval of the developed plan. Upon approval of the action plan, it receives the status of a mandatory document for the teaching staff. From that moment on, the next function of management – the organization comes into force. This function provides for the establishment of a specific structure of students and educators in management, organization of their mutual relationships and behaviours, and facilitating the implementation of the school's annual work plan. Organization is the activity of the governing body that creates and regulates the organizational structure of the management system, which is essential for the effective implementation of the decisions made by the governing body. The organizational function of management is implemented through the following operations: 1) definition of specific duties in accordance with the plan; 2) maintaining a proper work division; 3) establishment of cooperation; 4) increasing responsibility for labour motivation and common goal realization. Increasing the effectiveness of the system of organizational relationships at all levels is one of the important issues of democratization of management. In order to democratize the organizational function, it is necessary to create new organizational forms of management, to include new management subjects, to identify new functions of these subjects, their relations and relationships. In fact, this approach allows the school to transform itself into a self-management system that develops democratic principles of management. After the implementation of the organizational activity, it is sometimes accompanied by a parallel control (monitoring), including an analysis and recording of the school's activities. In some studies, control- regulation and accounting are presented as independent and in some cases as joint management functions. The school experience shows that it is not acceptable to separate and bar them, since they are the necessary chunks of the same process. The purpose of the oversight function is to reveal the current situation in each of the areas within the management structure, to obtain the necessary information and, thus, to improve the educational process. The head of the school, analyzing the results of operational information related to control and intra-school management, begins to perform a regulatory function in accordance with the general findings. The control function is also implemented through a number of operations: 1) the content of the control is defined; 2) control is carried out directly; 3) control data is collected and processed; 4) Based on the results of the analysis, appropriate measures are developed and implemented. Another function of the pedagogical process – pedagogical analysis, which plays an important role in the structure of the management cycle, is of particular relevance. According to the researchers, "any management cycle consisting of interrelated functions begins and ends with pedagogical analysis" (Pashayev & Rustamov, 2012, p. 432). The effectiveness of management depends on the school principal's profound knowledge of the technology of pedagogical analysis. Experience shows that analysis

of the goals and objectives of the delayed or incompetent analysis in the activities of the school principal can lead to uncertainty and even ineffectiveness of the decisions made. The main purpose of pedagogical analysis is to study the state and trends of the pedagogical process, to make objective assessments of its results, and to develop recommendations for it to regulate the management system. Compared to other management functions, pedagogical analysis appears to be less effective. In fact, it requires the person to have the maximum intellectual tension, analytical thinking that is formed to compare, summarize, systematize, and synthesize pedagogical facts and events.

Discussion

Democratization is often viewed as a tool and process, but we think it would be more appropriate to look at the principle that applies to all functions of management and all types of activities. Practice shows that democratic spirit in school can be built on egalitarianism and human trust. Democratization of school management can be achieved by electronizing management, sharing powers, duties and responsibilities. Digitalization of intra-school management plays an important role in enhancing the level of professionalism in management. The democratization of intra-school management has shifted all relationships from “manager-worker” to cooperative stage, requires refusing formula – “The director is always right!” which chokes the creativity and innovation. At this time the democratic leadership style (“the truth on the side of Who is right”) is being established, scientific and cognitive and methodological development of the teacher is being provided, and the level of professionalism is rising. The style of democratic leadership is based on the principles of mutual respect, humanism, equality and justice. The main means of democratic style are persuasion, request, advice, cooperation. Democratic style allows for honest communication, creating a healthy learning environment, maintaining a person's sense of personal dignity, enhancing the authority of the executive and, most importantly, effective and quality management. Democratization in management implies an evaluation of the initiative, competence, responsibility, freedom, and originality of the employees.

The way to democratize the school is to modernize the organizational structure of school management. The modernization envisages the transition to a hierarchical multi-dimensional structure of school, including representatives of public authorities, student collectives, teachers and parents in the management process.

The democratization and decentralization of management are essential to the work of the school. However, experience shows that excessive decentralization of management, like excessive centralization, is a threat to school development (Orujova, 2013). In each concrete case, there should be an average threshold for centralization and decentralization. Optimal dimensions of self-management and collegiality,

subordination and coordination, engagement and coordination, the exercise of power in management, and the coordination of joint management and self-management are to be expected. Thus, the task of the school staff and education management authorities is to determine the optimal relationship between the administrative and collective control of each participant of the educational process and ensure their cohesion. Providing this cohesion is an important way to democratize intra-school management.

In the context of the democratization of intra-school management, school team members – school leaders, teachers, students, parents – play two roles as subjects and objects of management in relation to one another and the collective (Quliyeva, 2008). This, in turn, proves that there is a direct and opposite relationship between them, as well as information that provides that link. The effectiveness of this process is directly related to the formation of participants' management skills and habits. Given that pupils constitute a weak link in the management of the school team, it is important that their knowledge, skills, and habits in management are gained by the community. Society needs citizens who can live and work in a democracy.

The school principal plays a crucial role in improving the management skills of the pedagogical process participants. The principal of the school should prepare school activists (teachers, pupils, parents) to help other participants of the intra-school management acquire the necessary knowledge, skills and habits. The development of the school team is shaped by the level of perfection, the general culture and the social activity of the school principal. Different pedagogical teams differ from each other with different levels of management. The school staff may adopt certain standards for their activities only to fully disclose their specifics. At the same time, the school staff must not only violate existing laws governing the interests of the community, school staff, pupils and parents, but at the same time, this right is granted, first of all, to the supreme body of intra-school management – the general meeting of the school staff.

Conclusion

The following results can be deduced:

1. The democratization of school management depends on scientifically organized intra-school management, which promotes the management activity of all members of the teaching staff.
2. The active participation of all members of the school's teaching staff depends on the creation of conditions for constructive criticism and self-criticism at the school, the wide use of various forms and methods to encourage the work of the staff, the proper evaluation of their work, and the promotion of healthy competition among participants in the educational process.

3. One of the tools for democratization of management should be the control and evaluation of the activities of both the director and the staff. The form of self-monitoring should also be developed, and teachers should be more confident and trusting, and pedagogical monitoring should be used effectively to avoid mistakes in assessing the performance of staff.

4. The effectiveness of the democratization of intra-school management depends on the creation of a democratic and healthy learning environment in the school and the transformation of the school into an open society for all participants in the educational process.

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